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Project Coordinator: Joakim Dillner
Organisation: KI
E-mail: Joakim.Dillner@ki.se

Work Package 3
An established cohort setting for long-term exposure evaluation

Work package Leader: Matti Lehtinen
Organisation: TAUH
E-Mail: matti.lehtinen@tuni.fi

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		screening cohort information.		
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Executive Summary

In this deliverable, we describe the established settings of datasets from two EU countries, namely Finland and Sweden, for a combined evaluation of the extent of sexually transmitted human papillomaviruses infections (and *Chlamydia trachomatis* infection in the Finnish data) exposure as a cumulative, calendar-time- and age-dependent exposure(s) of the population for up to eight years.

The Finnish HPV Vaccine Cohort (F-vac) trial and follow-up consist of serial cervical HPV and *Chlamydia trachomatis* results among 20,513 initially consented at the age of 14 and most with a subsequent follow-up at 18, 22, 25 and 28 years of age (total N=60,000). All the participants are healthy volunteers and have signed an informed consent for sampling and analysis covering the intervention and the follow-up phases (Lehtinen et al., 2015; Louvanto et al., 2020; Pimenoff et al., 2023). The trial is approved by the Finnish National and the Pirkanmaa Hospital District Ethical Review Boards for Matti Lehtinen at Tampere University. The established setting of the F-vac cohort and described F-vac variables (metadata) are registered in the CSC Fairdata data catalogue (<https://etsin.fairdata.fi/>), embedded in the HEAP data catalogue. Use of this population-wise HPV vaccination data is governed according to the Finnish Biobank Act §26 & §27 following the Findata (www.findata.fi) instructions. Access to identifiable, individual-level data is possible for research. It requires a GDPR-compatible research request approval from the F-vac Data Access Committee and appropriate ethical review boards.

The Swedish cervical screening cohort (NkCx) contains serial cervical HPV genotype data from over 600,000 women screened every 3-7 years between the ages of 23 and 70 as part of the national HPV screening program for women born between 1993 and 1998 (Elfström et al., 2016). The cohort started in 2011 and has collected samples from virtually all women participating in the cervical screening (83% of the population ages 23-64), which is over 1 million cervical cell samples from about 600,000 women (Elfström et al., 2016; Hortlund et al., 2018). The NkCx Cohort provides information about the primary results from testing cervical samples for HPV, cytology, and histopathology and data on any secondary research analyses performed on the samples. The samples part of the data are available for external researchers, provided appropriate permissions from the Swedish Ethical Review Authority, and the Region Stockholm Medical Biobank have been approved.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	2
Introduction	4
Cohort datasets	5
3.2.1 The Finnish HPV Vaccination Cohort (F-VAC).....	5
3.2.2 The Swedish cervical screening cohort (NkCx).....	8
Summary	10
References	11

Introduction

Deliverable 3.2 comprises documentation demonstrating the combined availability and use of the Finnish HPV vaccination cohort (F-VAC) of 20,513 initially consented women with eight years of follow-up data with HPV and *C. trachomatis* exposure analysis (Lehtinen et al., 2015; Pimenoff et al., 2023) and the Swedish Cervical Screening cohort (NkCx) of HPV exposure data across the Swedish female population (Elfström et al., 2016). These serial population-level sexually transmitted infection exposure datasets provide a setting for comprehensive and pertinent assessment of the population's cumulative, calendar-time- and age-dependent exposure(s).

The history of F-VAC (Lehtinen et al., 2015; Louvanto et al., 2020) stems from 2007-2018 with due, documented consenting trial procedures and ongoing sample recruitment. The trial dataset (total N=60,000) consists of serial cervical HPV and *Chlamydia trachomatis* results and relevant metadata among 20,513 initially consented at the age of 14 and largely with follow-up data at the 18, 22, 25 and 28 years of age.

The Swedish cervical screening cohort (NkCx) has enrolled over 600,000 women born between 1993 and 1998 at about 1 million screening visits, with one cervical sample taken per screening visit. The cohort started in 2011 and has collected samples from virtually all women participating in the cervical screening in Sweden. Each year, the cohort is associated with individual-level data from the Swedish national cervical screening registry, such that the cohort database contains individual birth dates, sampling dates and cytological, HPV and histological results.

Specific sections

Through the ethical review board approval, the informed consented, and through data protection/authority GDPR approvals, WP3 makes two ongoing longitudinal HPV cohorts, one from Finland and one from Sweden, available as aggregated FAIR data deposits and upon a research plan-driven request from the data controller or data access committee also a pseudo-anonymised data in a GDPR-compatible format is available from Fairdata platform for comprehensive sexually transmitted infections exposure studies.

Cohort datasets

3.2.1 The Finnish HPV Vaccination Cohort (F-VAC)

The community-randomized Finnish HPV vaccination cohort [NCT00534638], conducted by Professor Matti Lehtinen and his group from Tampere University in Finland, is a comprehensive and pioneering study aimed at evaluating the effectiveness and long-term outcomes of the bivalent HPV vaccine in the Finnish female population. The study is based on a cohort of 20,513 consented women (Figure 1) who were vaccinated at the age of 14 years between 2007 and 2015 against the most oncogenic HPVs and who were followed up for fifteen years for tracking the incidence of HPV-related diseases, such as cervical cancer or related pre-cancer lesions (Lehtinen et al., 2015; Louvanto et al., 2020; Pimenoff et al., 2023).

Figure 1. Finnish HPV vaccination cohort of 20,513 initially consented women with fifteen years of follow-up data since HPV vaccination at the age of 14 years old with HPV and *C. trachomatis* exposure data available (Lehtinen et al., 2015; Pimenoff et al., 2023)

The HPV vaccination cohort study is unique in its scope and scale, and it provides a wealth of data on the real-world effectiveness of the HPV vaccine at the Finnish population level. Professor Lehtinen and his group have published several groundbreaking papers based on the

cohort, including studies on the population-level HPV prevalences, vaccine's impact on cervical cancer incidence, the long-term persistence of vaccine-induced immunity, the safety and effectiveness of the vaccine and vaccine effect on the ecology of oncogenic HPVs (Lehtinen et al., 2012; Lehtinen et al., 2015; Gray et al., 2021; Lehtinen et al., 2023; Pimenoff et al., 2023).

The findings of the Finnish HPV vaccination cohort have had a significant impact on global public health policy on HPV vaccination and screening and have helped to demonstrate the safety and efficacy of the HPV vaccine (Lehtinen et al., 2012; Louvanto et al., 2020; Vänska et al., 2020; Lehtinen & Pimenoff, 2022). The cohort has also served as a model for other large-scale vaccination studies, and studies using the cohort data have contributed to our understanding of the long-term effects and benefits of HPV vaccination (Pimenoff et al., 2023).

The established F-VAC cohort data described here consists of the following:

- A total of 20,513 consented young adolescent Finnish women who were resident in 33 randomised Finnish communities (Figure 1).
- These women were from birth cohorts 1992-95 and were HPV vaccinated between 12-15 years old (Figure 1).
- Of the 20,513 consented women, 6,958 were HPV, and *C. trachomatis* screened at the 18- and 22-years-of-age (Figure 1).

The available data and metadata for the established setting of the Finnish HPV vaccination cohort consist of the following descriptive from all 20,513 initially consented women and serially for the 6,958 follow-up individuals at 18- and 22 years of age (Table 1).

Table 1. Dataset descriptives.

- Residential history (by municipality until age 22).
- Consent date (vaccination trial, ages 12-15; screening trial, ages 22).
- Vaccination date (HPV16/18 and HBV vaccines, 3x2 doses at ages 12-15 and 18).
- Health questionnaire data (at ages 15, 18, and 22).
- Follow-up visits/sampling date (at ages 18, 22).
- Cervical HPV6/11/16/18/31/33/35/39/45/51/52/56/58/59/66 genotypes and serology.
- Chlamydia trachomatis screening results at ages 18-22.

The F-VAC Data Records include residential and vaccination history, a broad HPV infection status at DNA and serology level as well as comprehensive cervical cytology and histology data, *Chlamydia trachomatis* testing results (ages 18 and 22) and smoking status (ages 25 and 28). Use of this population-wise HPV vaccination data is governed according to the Finnish Biobank Act §26 & §27 following the Findata (www.findata.fi) instructions. All procedures performed in these studies involving data from human participants follow the ethical standards of the institutional research committee and with the 1964 Helsinki Declaration and its later amendments or comparable ethical standards.

The established setting of the F-vac cohort and described F-vac variables (metadata) are registered in the CSC Fairdata data catalogue (<https://etsin.fairdata.fi/>), embedded in the HEAP data catalogue. An example of the F-vac database descriptives is also provided here in Table 2. Access to pseudo-anonymised and aggregated sample data is possible through the Data Access Committee of the particular datasets in the CSC Fairdata catalogue (see <http://urn.fi/urn:nbn:fi:att:75298693-32d4-4d33-9bd2-8b376bd1e684>).

Table 2. Dataset features available for F-Vac.

- Pseudonymised identification number
- Date birth (yy, mm)
- Dates of consents
- Data on the allocation of the randomized interventions (vaccination)
- Data on the allocation of the randomized interventions (screening)
- Dates of sampling (cervix)
 - Data on cervical HPV typing results
 - Data on cervical cytological results
 - Data on cervical histopathological results
 - Data on cervical treatment results
- Dates of sampling (oral)
 - Data on oral HPV typing results
- Dates of sampling (serum)
 - Data on HPV antibody results
- Birth registry linkage data
 - Numbers of pregnancies and deliveries
 - Numbers of abortions
 - Numbers of miscarriages
- Cancer Registry linkage data
 - Data on incident cancers
 - Data on incident cervical precancer (HSIL)
- Hospital discharge registry linkage data
 - New onset autoimmune diseases
- Due dates of register linkages
- Residential history
- Intervention history by arm
- Anonymised questionnaire data by the intervention arm
 - Data on living conditions, life habits, risk-taking behaviour

Access to identifiable, individual-level data is also possible for research. It requires permission from the Data Access Committee (DAC) for F-vac. Applying for DAC permission requires a research plan and the applicant's affiliation with a recognised research institute. International research groups are encouraged to contact the DAC members of the particular dataset to assist

with preparing the application. The application forms and instructions can be found at (<https://etsin.fairdata.fi/>).

The procedure to obtain data associated with the samples is the same as for accessing identifiable data (as explained above). All the cohort participants are originally healthy volunteers and have signed an informed consent covering the intervention and the follow-up phases. Further analysis of the specimen, together with metadata, can also be requested.

Following the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) the cohort is approved for research by the Pirkanmaa Hospital District Ethical Review Board (R07113M/2007, R11058/2011, R13149/2014, R19136/2020) and the anonymised metadata with HPV, *C. trachomatis* and cancer association information is deposited into the CSC Fairdata data catalogue and is available through GDPR-compatible research request from the FAIR data portal (<https://etsin.fairdata.fi/>). The process for such permissions can be complicated. Thus, the DAC committee supports such projects as research collaboration, assisting the researchers in filing the Data request and data permit applications following the instructions for data protection of individuals and data security (<https://www.findata.fi/en/services/services-for-customers/>). Moreover, if complementary data from other registries are needed, DAC for F-vac can offer researchers advice on obtaining such data through registry linkages.

3.2.2 Swedish Cervical Screening (NkCx)

The Swedish Cervical Cancer Screening Registry (NkCx) (Elfström et al., 2016; Hortlund et al., 2018) manages around 1.2 million sample data from over 600,000 Swedish women stems from the Swedish cervical screening program to prevent the occurrence of invasive cervical cancer in the population. The program started in 1964 and was expanded nationally between 1967 and 1973. Every woman resident in Sweden is called for cervical screening every 3-7 years between the ages of 23 and 70.

The Central screening laboratory of the Stockholm region (today the Center for Cervical Cancer Elimination) started a cervical screening cohort enrollment and sampling in 2011 to archive the residual cervical samples taken using liquid-based cytology at - 30 C. It is a cohort of liquid-based samples of cervical cells. The cells are preserved in a liquid preservative, which has many more medical research uses. The cohort contains over one million samples from more than 600 000 women (Table 3). The annual growth of the cohort ranged between 40,000 to 200,000 new samples (paused during the COVID-19 pandemic) from new sampling occasions added each year.

Table 3. Swedish cervical cancer screening samples (published in 2022).

Ages	Number of women with samples	Number samples
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23-30	200,605	268,607
31-49	335,761	539,920
50-70	172,744	232,371
All	623,993	1,040,898

The NKCx, is part of the cervical screening program's evidence-based surveillance and quality assurance and contains data on all cervical tests (cytologies, HPV tests, histopathologies), personal invitations and consents from all screening units in the country resulting in 100% national coverage (Table 4). Key quality indicators (e.g., population test coverage, diagnostic profiles, population coverage of invitations, and proportion of women with abnormal tests that are followed up) and basic statistics are reported to each region's organised cervical screening programs.

Table 4. Swedish cervical cancer screening samples results (published in 2022).

Ages	Cytology status of the sample		HPV-status of sample	
	Normal cytology	Abnormal cytology	Negative	Positive
23-30	190,344	21,657	55,045	29,417
31-49	188,454	18,346	327,612	42,814
50-70	56,562	3,746	168,789	13,402
All	435,360	43,749	551,446	85,633

Requests for access to the data are sent to the Swedish national cervical screening registry at info@nkcx.se. Identifiable data or biospecimens require permission from the Swedish Ethical Review Agency. At least one co-applicant in the ethical permission application needs to be a citizen of Sweden. The Swedish cervical screening cohort in HEAP aims to evaluate internal biotic exposure factors in women as measured in cervical exfoliated cells. The cohort can provide samples from women with healthy cervix, pre-neoplastic lesions, and cancer, with associated data. The developed bioinformatics and ML analysis tools described in D6.3 will facilitate the research on this cohort.

All data from the screening process is registered in the NKCx to evaluate the quality of the screening program. Data collection is population-based (all women in the population). Opting out is possible and quite rare (<1 woman/1,000,000). Identifiable data in NKCx, to be used for research purposes, requires an ethical permit issued by the ethical review agency and an application for data sent to the Registry to be reviewed by the Steering Group.

The Sensitive Data catalogue contains a complete description of the NKCx variables (www.csc.fi). It is accessible by requesting an account. An example of the NKCx database variables is provided through https://nkcx.se/research_e.htm.

Some aggregated data (not identifiable) are openly accessible through https://nkcx.se/qind_e.htm. Requesting aggregated data has no restrictions for research and other purposes and is submitted to the registry chairperson (https://nkcx.se/contact_e.htm). Access to identifiable, individual-level data is also possible for research. It requires:

- Permission from the Swedish Ethical Review Authority. Applying to the Swedish Ethical Review Authority requires at least one Swedish citizen to be a co-applicant. International teams are encouraged to contact the registry at info@nkcx.se, and the registry will then assist with preparing the application.
- Permission from the Steering Group of the NKCx. The application forms and instructions are at https://nkcx.se/research_en.htm.

Access to pseudo-anonymised and aggregated sample data is possible through *figshare* (<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.24799524.v1>). The variables in this dataset are described in Table 5.

The procedure to obtain data associated with the samples is the same as for accessing identifiable data (as explained above). In addition, it requires permission from the regional biobank centre of Region Stockholm. If complementary data from other registries are needed, NKCx can offer researchers advice on obtaining such data through registry linkages.

Table 5. Variables in the available dataset in *figshare*.

Variable	Description of variables
Sequence_number_women	External identifier to link a woman with her samples
Sequence_number_sample	External identifier to link samples to a woman
Sample_year	Sampling year
Age	Age range (8 years)
Screening_sample	“Yes”: Organized screening, “No”: Another cell test
Cytology_test	“1” if the test was done
HPV_test	“1” if the test was done
Cytology_result	“Normal” or “Abnormal” if Cytology_test is “1”
HPV_result	“Negative” or “Positive” if HPV_test is “1”

Summary

Here, we describe the established setting datasets from two EU countries, namely Finland and Sweden, for a combined evaluation of the extent of sexually transmitted infections exposure as a cumulative, calendar-time- and age-dependent exposure(s) of the populations for up to eight years.

The Finnish F-VAC trial and follow-up consist of serial cervical HPV and *Chlamydia trachomatis* results and metadata among 6958 women from the 20,513 initially consented at 12-15-22-25-28 years of age and further screened for genital HPV and *C. trachomatis* infection. Following the European GDPR, the cohort is approved for research by the Finnish Medical District Ethical Review Board, and the anonymised metadata with HPV, *C. trachomatis* and cancer association information is available in the CSC Fairdata platform through GDPR-compatible research request to the data controller in Finland.

The HEAP Swedish cervical screening cohort contains serial cervical HPV genotype data from over 600,00 women screened every 3-7 years between the ages of 23 and 70 as part of the national HPV screening program for women born between 1993 and 1998 (Elfström et al., 2016). The cohort started in 2011 and has collected samples from 83% of the population ages 23-64, with over 1 million cervical cell samples from about 600,000 women (Elfström et al., 2016). Following the European GDPR, the cohort is approved for research by the Swedish Medical District Ethical Review Board, and the anonymised data is available provided the GDPR-compatible research request approved by the Swedish national cervical screening registry at info@nkcx.se and associated Steering Group of the NKCx.

These Finnish and Swedish longitudinal screening data will enable a parallel assessment of similarities and differences in the transmissibility and oncogenic association of the circulating internal and external biotic exposures (e.g. related sexually transmitted infections) following population-level HPV vaccine implementations or screening, respectively, in the countries above. These results will be the basis for the future population health policies for cancer screening design of HPV-vaccinees and the herd effect-protected non-HPV vaccinated women and men in Europe.

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